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Abstracts Track 2

Accessibility to what? Broadening the discussion through essay filmmaking with Latin-American migrant women in the Randstad region.

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This paper presents my personal journey in developing a methodology to approach transport and accessibility. From the outset, it was clear that I would apply a participatory methodology. A central characteristic of participatory (action) research is that personal and critical reflection is an integral part of the investigation. As will become clear, I have chosen a rather artistic way of generating knowledge, particularly essay filmmaking. This artistic dimension is no coincidence, and the present contribution offers a personal reflection of how art influenced my academic work.

The methodology aims to construct collectively an audio-visual piece where Latin-American migrant women in Randstad's voices are included and heard as a result of the experience. The objective is not just studying "them" with the "othering" gaze but instead using community-based and co-creation methodologies that empower the

communities through research. This study is in progress and will take place between April and July 2023. To apply the resulting methodology, we will work in articulation with different spaces and networks that already work with Latin-American women in the Netherlands. Six vignettes, are used to bring structure in my journey. In each step, reference is made to a piece of art, an art event, or an encounter with an artist (or scholar who works with arts), and this is linked to an academic concept (positionality, liminality, subjectification...). Taken together, these vignettes illustrate how methodology, conceptualisation and art production co-develop and lead to a specific outcome using a "Bricolage" assemblage. It also illustrates how personal encounters and experiences shape my research process.

Keywords: Accessibility, narratives, personal journey, Latin-American women, filmmaking